

ISic1287

I.Sicily inscription 1287

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.10.22

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 8751

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140777

1. Αὐρήλις Βιτάλης νῦν ἐνθάδε
2. κεῖμαι, | κόσμου πλάνην προ-
3. λιπῶν εἰς αἰώνιον οἶκον ἀ-
4. νελθῶν, | μηδένα λυπήσας ὁ-
5. μαλὸν βίον ὧδε διάγω· ἔζησα
6. δὲ ἔτη ξε.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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